

The Effect of Motivation and Leadership on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at The Directorate General of Rural Area Development Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of motivation and leadership on employee performance at the directorate general of rural area development, determine the effect of motivation and leadership on job satisfaction at the directorate general of rural area development, determine the effect of motivation on employee performance at the directorate general of rural area development, and determine the influence of leadership on employee performance at the directorate general of rural area development, knowing the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance at the directorate general for rural area development, knowing the effect of motivation on employee performance at the directorate general for rural area development through job satisfaction, knowing leadership on employee performance at the directorate general for regional development rural areas through job satisfaction. This research was conducted on employees of the directorate general of rural area development at the ministry of villages, development of disadvantaged areas, and transmigration. The data collection technique used a saturated sample involving 163 civil servants at the directorate general of rural area development and then analysis using path analysis.

The results of this study indicate the findings: first, motivation and leadership affect employee performance; both motivation and leadership affect job satisfaction; the three motivations affect employee performance; the fourth leadership affects employee performance; fifth, job satisfaction affects employee performance; the six motivations have a more significant direct influence on employee performance, so it can be said that the job satisfaction variable is not intervening; The seven leaderships have a more significant influence on employee performance, so it can be said that the job satisfaction variable is not intervening.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Based on Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 12 of 2015 concerning the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration, the Directorate General of Rural Area Development has the task of carrying out the formulation and implementation of policies in the field of planning, rural area development, and rural area economic development following the provisions and laws applicable.

The Directorate General of Rural Area Development is one of the Directorate Generals at the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration, which carries out the vision and mission of the President of the Republic of Indonesia's vision and mission equitable and just development (Gini Index). To support the achievement of the vision and mission of the President of the Republic of Indonesia, the Directorate General of Rural Area development requires a State Civil Apparatus that is professional. With integrity, therefore, the Directorate General of Rural Area Development continues to gradually strive to improve employees' competence and capabilities to improve employee performance and organizational performance. Employees are expected to have competencies that include soft skills, hard skills, knowledge, attitude and capability to increase work productivity.

According to Law Number 5 of 2015 concerning State Civil Apparatus. State Civil Apparatus, hereinafter abbreviated as ASN, is a Civil Servants and Government Employees with Work Agreements who work for government agencies. The State Civil

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Apparatus is entrusted with carrying out public service tasks, government duties, and specific development tasks. Therefore, the government needs to build a State Civil Apparatus that has integrity, is professional, neutral and free from political intervention, is free from practices of corruption, collusion, and nepotism, and can provide public services for the community and can carry out its role as an element of national unity and integrity based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

The Performance of State Civil Apparatus Employees in carrying out their main duties and functions and other tasks is expected to continue to increase from year to year. The statement by the President of the Republic of Indonesia on August 17, 2019, in commemoration of the Independence Day of the Republic of Indonesia, stated that the development of human resources is an essential key in accelerating the development of the Republic of Indonesia. Therefore, improving the Performance of the State Civil Apparatus is an essential point in measuring the success of human resource development within the organization.

Therefore, in carrying out governance arrangements and structuring the bureaucracy and service quality to realize a world-class government system, government organizations must be able to create competent human resources to increase productivity and respond appropriately to the exponential development of technological advances time. According to Peter Diamandis, exponential technological progress is divided into six stages: Digitalization, Deception, Disruption, Dematerialization, Demonetization and Democratization.

Human Resource Development is an organization's way of maintaining the existence of all components of the organization. An organization must be able to optimize the capabilities of its human resources so that the achievement of goals can be carried out, but this is not simple, it requires a good understanding of the organization, there needs to be a mature development strategy so that the human resources of an organization are used as needed. Therefore, Human Resource Development is one of the priorities in supporting every activity, especially in the office sector carried out by the government and the private sector. Hasibuan (2003) says that: "Employees are the company's main asset because, without their participation, company activities will not occur. Employees play an active role in setting plans, systems, processes, and goals to be achieved.

One aspect of the strength of human resources in an organization is employee performance. Performance is the main issue that needs to be emphasized so that organizational activities run smoothly. Good performance describes the effectiveness of implementing organizational activities. Performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity/program/policy in realizing the goals, objectives, mission and vision of the organization contained in the strategic planning of an organization.

Mangkunegara (2015) "the notion of performance (work achievement) is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties following the responsibilities given to him." Prawirosentono (2008), "Performance is the result of work that a person or group of people can achieve in an organization, following their respective authorities and responsibilities, to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and following morals and ethics.

From the data on employee performance of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development above, it can be seen that there has been a decline in employee performance from 2017 to 2019. The decline in employee performance is marked by not increasing employee performance from year to year and not achieving employee performance targets in 2018 and 2019.

Fiscal Year	Employee Performance Realization	Employee Performance Target
2018	87	89
2019	86,7	91

From this phenomenon, it should be suspected that there is a problem of decreasing employee performance at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development caused by several factors in carrying out the work. Because the employee's performance target is not achieved, it will reduce the assessment of SPIP (Government Internal Control System) and Bureaucratic Reform.

Employee performance is one factor that plays an important role in achieving organizational goals and individual goals. As a State Civil Apparatus, of course, the performance of his employees is expected to continue to increase from time to time. In order to be able to provide services and support government policies better from time to time following their responsibilities as a State Civil Apparatus.

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According to Robbins (2001), in employee work, motivation is an important factor in encouraging an employee to work. Motivation is an individual's willingness to put forth a high effort to achieve organizational goals. There are three key elements in motivation, namely effort, organizational goals and needs. An effort is a measure of intensity. If someone is motivated, he will try his best to achieve the goal, but not necessarily, high effort will result in high performance. Therefore, it takes the intensity and quality of these efforts and is focused on organizational goals. Needs are internal conditions that give rise to drives, where unsatisfied needs will cause tensions that stimulate impulses from within the individual. This impulse gives rise to search behavior to find a particular goal. If it turns out that there is a need, there will be a reduction in voltage. Motivated employees are in a state of tension and seek to reduce tension by expending effort.

According to Simamora (2004:510), motivation is a function of the individual's expectation that certain efforts will produce a level of performance, producing the desired reward or result. Mangkunegara (2005: 61) states that "Motivation is formed from the attitude of employees in dealing with work situations in the company (situation)". Motivation is a condition or energy that moves employees directed or directed to achieve the company's organizational goals. The mental attitude of employees who are pro and positive towards the work situation strengthens the motivation in doing work to achieve maximum performance from outside oneself, especially from the organization where he works.

Motivated employees will make positive choices to do something that can satisfy their desires. Motivation can spur employees to work hard so that they can achieve the main goals of the organization. According to Usman (2013), motivation is the urge that a person has to do something, while the motive is the need, desire (wish), urge (desire) or impulse. Motivation is an impulse possessed by an individual that can stimulate to take actions or something that is the basis or reason for a person to behave or do something. Giving employees motivation cannot be separated from the role of a leader in behaving and motivating employees. According to Robbins (2007:173), leader behavior will provide motivation as long as it makes subordinates feel the need for satisfaction in achieving effective performance and provides the teachings, direction, support, and rewards needed for effective performance.

According to Wukir (2013:134), leadership is the art of motivating and influencing a group of people to act towards a common goal. Meanwhile, according to Samsudin (2009: 287), leadership can be interpreted as convincing and moving others to want to work together under his leadership as a team to achieve a specific goal. Then according to Rachmawati (2004), leadership can be interpreted as the ability to influence the group towards the achievement of goals or an effort to use an influencing and non-coercive style to motivate individuals in achieving goals. Robbins (2007) recognizes four leader behaviors: directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented. According to Rivai (2004), "Leadership is the process of influencing in determining organizational goals, motivating the behavior of followers to achieve goals and influencing the group and its culture."

Good leadership will create high motivation within each subordinate, with this motivation will lead to morale that can improve the performance of subordinates. Leadership has a very close relationship with motivation. The success of a leader in moving others to achieve the goals that have been set is very dependent on the authority and ability to create motivation in every subordinate, colleague, or leader of the leader himself. The lack of a leadership role in creating unified communication and providing employee coaching will lead to a low level of employee performance.

Good motivation and leadership have not only an impact on employee performance but also employee job satisfaction. Creating job satisfaction is not easy because job satisfaction can be created if the variables that influence it to include work motivation, leadership, and organizational culture/company, can be appropriately accommodated and accepted by all employees in an organization/company.

Daft (2012) asserts that "job satisfaction is related to one's feelings or attitudes about the work itself, salary, promotion or educational opportunities, supervision, co-workers, workload and others. In this case, what is meant by this attitude is all things related to work such as supervision, salary, working conditions, experience with skills, fair and non-discriminatory work assessments, good social relations in work, prompt resolution of complaints and good treatment from the leadership towards employees.

According to Ramayah (2001) and Janssen (2001) in Koesmono (2005:28) suggests that a leader will be very concerned about the aspect of job satisfaction because he has a moral responsibility, whether the leader can provide a good environment to his employees and believe that the behavior of workers who satisfied will make a positive contribution to the organization. Leaders perceive their efforts and performance to be successful when fairness in rewards provides job satisfaction and performance levels. A balanced work situation will increase feelings of control over work-life and result in job satisfaction so that managers/leaders have a responsibility to increase their subordinates' job satisfaction to make a positive contribution to their organization.

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The results of the pre-survey related to the relationship between motivation, leadership, job satisfaction and employee performance can predict that there is an influence between motivation, leadership and job satisfaction on employee performance in the Directorate General of Rural Area Development. The relationship between the four variables above is also supported by several studies, including Kelimeda, Hairudin, Ridwan and Dalle (2018), which states that motivation and job satisfaction affect employee performance. Bernanthos' research (2018) states that motivation and leadership affect employee satisfaction and performance directly or indirectly.

The relationship between motivation, leadership and employee job satisfaction is also supported by research by Santie, Tuerah, Biran, Psandaran (2018) which states that motivation and leadership affect employee job satisfaction and research by Runi, Ramli, Nujum and Kalla (2017) states that motivation and leadership effect on employee job satisfaction.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Employee Performance

The term performance comes from job performance or actual performance (job performance or actual achievement achieved by someone). Mangkunegara (2015) "the notion of performance (work achievement) is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

According to Prawirosentono (2008), "performance is the result of work that a person or group of people can achieve in an organization, following their respective authorities and responsibilities, to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and following morals as well as ethics". According to Sutrisno (2011) "Performance is a person's success in carrying out tasks, work results that a person or group of people can achieve in an organization following their respective authorities and responsibilities or about how a person is expected to function and behave following the assigned tasks charged to him as well as the quantity, quality and time used in carrying out the task. Then Robbins (2007) defines "performance is a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a job".

At this time, the world is undergoing changes that continue to grow rapidly. This change is not only felt by the private sector but also in government organizations. Government organizations must carry out significant reforms to successfully carry out their duties and functions in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0. The existence of advanced technology in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 is a challenge for employees to improve their performance so that their career development is good while working and has high productivity.

Measuring employee performance can be done in several ways. Job standards can be determined from the content of a job and serve as the basis for evaluating each job. According to Bangun (2012), a job can be measured through:

- a. Number of Jobs: This dimension shows the number of jobs produced by individuals or groups as requirements that become standard jobs;
- b. Quality of Work: Every employee in the company must meet certain requirements to be able to produce work according to the quality required by a particular job:
- c. Timeliness: Each job has different characteristics, for certain types of work must be completed on time, because it has a dependence on other jobs. In this dimension, employees are required to be able to complete their work on time.
- d. Attendance: A specific type of work requires employees to do it according to the specified time. The level of employee attendance determines employee performance in doing it.
- e. Cooperation Ability: For certain types of work, two or more employees may have to complete it, so cooperation between employees is required. Employee performance can be judged by their ability to cooperate with other co-workers.

B. Motivation

According to Robbins (2001) in employee work, motivation is one of the important factors in encouraging an employee to work. Motivation is an individual's willingness to put forth a high effort to achieve organizational goals. There are three key elements in motivation, namely effort, organizational goals and needs. The effort is a measure of intensity. If someone is motivated, then he will try his best to achieve the goal, but not necessarily, high effort will result in high performance. Therefore, it takes the intensity and quality of these efforts and is focused on organizational goals.

Needs are internal conditions that give rise to drives, where unsatisfied needs will cause tensions that stimulate impulses from within the individual. This impulse gives rise to search behavior to find a specific goal. If it turns out that there is a need, there will be a reduction in voltage. Motivated employees are in a state of tension and seek to reduce tension by expending effort,

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According to Simamora (2004:510), motivation is a function of the individual's expectation that certain efforts will produce a level of performance, producing the desired reward or result. Mangkunegara (2005: 61) states that "Motivation is formed from the attitude of employees in dealing with work situations in the company (situation)". Motivation is a condition or energy that moves employees who are directed or directed to achieve the company's organizational goals. The mental attitude of employees who are pro and positive towards the work situation is what strengthens the motivation in doing work to achieve maximum performance coming from outside a person, especially from the organization where he works.

According to Herzberg, cited by Sondang (2008: 107) developed a two-factor theory of motivation. According to this theory, two factors affect a person's work conditions, namely the satisfying factor, which is also called satisfier or intrinsic motivation and the health factor, which is also called dissatisfied or extrinsic motivation. This theory sees that two factors encourage employees to be motivated, namely intrinsic factors, namely the driving force that arises from within each person, and extrinsic factors, namely the driving force that comes from outside a person, especially from the organization where he works.

- a. As for Frederick Herzberg, 6 indicators of work motivation are as follows:
- b. Achievements. The possibility of members achieving work performance is little;
- c. Confession. The amount of recognition given to members for their performance;
- d. The Work Itself. The size of the challenges that members feel from their work;
- e. Responsibility. The size of the responsibility given to a member;
- f. Progress. It is unlikely that members can advance in their work;
- g. Development of Individual Potential. It is unlikely that members will develop in their work.

C. Leadership

According to Hasibuan (2009: 170), leadership is the way a leader influences the behavior of subordinates so that they are willing to work together and work productively to achieve organizational goals. According to Robbins (2007:173) leader behavior will provide motivation as long as it makes subordinates feel the need for satisfaction in achieving effective performance and provides the teachings, direction, support and rewards needed for effective performance. Robbert House in Robbins (2007:173) recognizes four leader behaviors, namely those with directive character, supporting character, participatory character and achievement-oriented.

Wukir (2013: 134) provides an understanding of leadership which is the art of motivating and influencing a group of people to act towards a common goal. Meanwhile, according to Samsudin (2009) leadership can be interpreted as the ability to convince and move others to want to work together under his leadership as a team to achieve a certain goal. Then according to Rachmawati (2004: 67), leadership can be interpreted as the ability to influence the group towards the achievement of goals or an effort to use an influencing style and not force to motivate individuals in achieving goals. According to Rivai, Darmasyah, and M Ramly (2014), leadership broadly includes influencing in determining organizational goals, motivating follower behavior to achieve goals, influencing to improve the group and its culture. Leadership is sometimes understood as the power to move and influence people. Leadership is a tool, means or process to persuade people to be willing to do something voluntarily.

There are three important implications contained in leadership, among others:

- a. Leadership involves other people, both from subordinates and followers.
- b. Leadership involves a balanced distribution of power between the leader and group members because group members are not powerless.
- c. The existence of the ability to use different forms of power to influence followers' behavior in various ways.

D. Job Satisfaction

According to Robbins and Judge (2015:78), job satisfaction is "a general attitude towards a person's work that shows the difference between the number of awards workers receive and the amount they believe they should receive". Job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects or aspects of one's work so that job satisfaction is not a single concept. A person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of the job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects (Hasibuan, 2005).

According to Ramayah (2001) and Janssen (2001) in Koesmono (2005:28) suggests that a leader will be very concerned about the aspect of job satisfaction because he has a moral responsibility, whether the leader can provide an excellent environment to his employees and believe that the behavior of workers who satisfied will make a positive contribution to the organization. Leaders perceive their efforts and performance to be successful when fairness in rewards provides levels of job satisfaction and performance. A balanced work situation will increase feelings of control over work-life and result in job satisfaction so that managers/leaders have a responsibility to increase their subordinates' job satisfaction to make a positive contribution to their organization.

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Richard et al. (2012) asserted that "job satisfaction is related to one's feelings or attitudes about the work itself, salary, promotion or educational opportunities, supervision, co-workers, workload and others. In this case, what is meant by this attitude is all things related to work such as supervision, salary, working conditions, experience with skills, fair and non-disadvantaging work assessments, good social relations in work, prompt resolution of complaints and good treatment from the leadership towards employees.

Sowmya and Panchanatham (2011) stated that job satisfaction could be measured using the following five indicators:

- a. Salary and promotion, in terms of salary measured by fairness in salary provision, the amount of salary received and the appropriateness of the reward for the work. While promotion is seen from opportunities to achieve position advancement.
- b. Organizational aspects, namely the attitudes possessed by employees towards organizational conditions. This can be measured by the feelings that employees have towards the organization and the treatments the organization has on employees.
- c. Leadership behavior, the ability of leaders to show concern for employees such as supervision and delivery of organizational policies.
- d. Work and working conditions indicate the degree to which job tasks are considered interesting and provide opportunities for learning and accepting responsibility.
- e. Co-worker behavior that can be measured by pleasant co-workers' behavior and communication between employees.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Research Sites

Data collection will be carried out at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development (Ditjen PKP) which is located on Jl. TMP. Kalibata, South Jakarta. The data processing and analysis as well as thesis preparation will also be carried out in Jakarta.

B. Research Design

This research is reminiscent of the explanatory analysis approach. This means that each variable presented in the hypothesis will be observed by testing the independent variable's causal relationship with the dependent variable.

C. Population and Sample

The research was conducted on the Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration. The population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects with certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions (Sugiyono, 2009). In this study, the population is Civil Servants in the Directorate General of Rural Area Development as many as 163 employees.

While the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population, if the population is large and the researcher is not able to study everything in the population, for example, due to limited funds, workforce and time, the researcher can use samples taken from that population (Sugiyono, 2009). The research sample was 163 respondents.

D. Data Source

To obtain concrete and objective data, research must be conducted on the problem under study. The steps that researchers take in data collection are:

Primary data is data obtained directly from the object of research. In this case, the primary data is obtained from field research; namely, the data collection method carried out by direct research on the object of research in question. Secondary data is data obtained indirectly from the object of research. In this case, secondary data is obtained from library research, namely data collection carried out by studying and understanding literature books created by authors who can be accounted for.

E. Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis is an activity after data from all respondents is collected. Data processing is collected, processed, and presented in tabular form to facilitate the author's management in preparing this proposal using classified secondary data to facilitate research. The data analysis technique used in this study is path analysis to analyze the pattern of relationships between variables to know the indirect effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable that is mediated by the intervening variable.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Motivation and Leadership on Employee Performance

The linear analysis model obtained the following simultaneous structural equations:

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$$Y = 0.728X_1 + 0.148X_2$$

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the calculated F value is 218,538 and a significant value of 0.00 is smaller than 0.05. This means that the variables of leadership and motivation affect employee performance simultaneously. The magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is known that the r squared value of 0.732 means that the leadership and motivation variables affect employee performance by 73.2%. In contrast, the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

2. Analysis of the influence of motivation and leadership on job satisfaction

The linear analysis model obtained the following simultaneous structural equations:

$$X_3 = 0.174 X_1 + 0.769 X_2$$

The calculated F value is 439,717 and a significant value of 0.00 is less than 0.05. This means that the variables of motivation and leadership affect job satisfaction simultaneously. The magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the intervening variable is known that the r-squared value of 0.846 means that the motivation and leadership variables affect employee performance by 84.6% while the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

3. Analysis of the Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance

The analysis of the influence of motivation on employee performance is known that the motivation coefficient is 0.852, the t value is 20.624. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the motivation variable affects the employee's performance partially. The magnitude of the influence of motivation on employee performance is known that the value of r squared is 0.724. This means that the influence of motivational variables on employee performance is 72.4% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

4. Analysis of the Effect of Leadership on Employee Performance

The analysis of leadership on employee performance is known that the leadership coefficient is 0.757, the t value is 14.698. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the leadership variable partially affects employee performance. The magnitude of the influence of leadership on employee performance is known to have an r squared value of 0.573. This means that the influence of the leadership variable on employee performance is 57.3%, and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

5. Analysis of the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

The analysis of the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance partially shows that the motivation coefficient is 0.878, the t value is 23,324. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the variable job satisfaction affects the performance of employees partially. The magnitude of job satisfaction on employee performance is known to have an r squared value of 0.770. This means that job satisfaction on employee performance is 77% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

6. Analysis of the Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction Variables

Based on path analysis, it is known that the effect of motivation on employee performance is 0.852. The effect of motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction is $0.915 \times 0.878 = 0.803$. In this case, the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect, so it can be said that the job satisfaction variable is not intervening.

7. Analysis of the Effect of Leadership on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction Variables

Based on path analysis, it is known that the influence of leadership on employee performance is 0.757. The influence of leadership on employee performance through job satisfaction is $0.818 \times 0.878 = 0.718$. In this case, the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect, so it can be said that the job satisfaction variable is not intervening.

V. DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Motivation and Leadership on Employee Performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that motivation and leadership affect employee performance together; motivation partially affects employee performance and leadership on employee performance. These results are in line with research conducted by Chandra and Priyono (2016) which states that leadership influences employee performance. Iganasius, Yuesti, Landra (2018) which state that motivation affects employee performance and Santie, Tuerah, Biran, Psandaran (2018) and Kelimeda, Hairudin, Ridwan and Dalle (2018) which state that leadership and motivation affect employee performance.

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2. The Influence of Motivation and Leadership on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that motivation and leadership affect job satisfaction together, motivation and leadership affect job satisfaction together. These results are in line with research conducted by Bernanthos (2018), which states that leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and motivation while leadership only positively affects employee performance.

3. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

According to Ramayah (2001) and Janssen (2001) in Koesmono (2005:28) suggests that a leader will be very concerned about aspects of job satisfaction because he has a moral responsibility, whether the leader can provide a satisfactory environment to his employees and believe that the behavior of satisfied will make a positive contribution to the organization based on the results of hypothesis testing it is known that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. This is following the research of Octaviannand, Pandjaitan and Kuswanto (2017) which states that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance and the results of this study are not following the research of Husein, Hanifah (2018) which states that job satisfaction does not affect employee performance.

4. The Influence of Motivation and Leadership on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction

From the results of hypothesis testing, it is also known that there is no indirect effect of motivation and leadership variables on employee performance through job satisfaction. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Runi, Ramli, Nujum and Kalla (2017), Bernanthos (2018) and Iganasius, Yuesti, Landra (2018), which state that motivation and leadership have an indirect influence through job satisfaction.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the influence of motivation and leadership on employee performance through job satisfaction at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Motivation and Leadership on Employee Performance

The findings of the research show that leadership and motivation affect employee performance together, meaning that employees who are an important key in an organization need good leadership at work and a leader who can provide motivation and direction to produce effective performance.

2. Motivation and Leadership on Job Satisfaction

The findings of the research show that leadership and motivation affect job satisfaction together, meaning that if motivation and leadership in an organization are considered well by the leadership, it will encourage high job satisfaction of company employees.

3. Motivation on Employee Performance

The findings of the study indicate that motivation affects employee performance, meaning that with motivation, employees of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development will try to achieve achievement, employees will feel recognized and cared for by the leadership, employees are motivated to complete tasks and the work itself with good results satisfactory, employees are responsible for the main tasks and functions, and employees feel confident that the organization can develop the potential of individual employees.

4. Leadership on Employee Performance

The findings of the study indicate that leadership affects employee performance, meaning that employees of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development tend to want to have a leader who can become a liaison/mediator or foster good communication with various parties, leadership who can provide direction, motivation, and information in assisting completion duties, leadership who has the experience, ability and a sense of responsibility for the duties of employees and understands the needs of employees.

5. Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

The study's findings indicate that job satisfaction affects employee performance, which means that the Directorate General of Rural Area Development is expected to provide opportunities for employees to develop themselves by attending education and training and providing adequate facilities and infrastructure. Employee job satisfaction is also affected by leadership behavior

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because employees need proportional support and motivation in completing the tasks and work assigned. Duties and jobs, helping employees develop and become better following the wishes of employees and a work environment that is supported by the behavior of co-workers.

6. Motivation on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction

The findings of this study indicate that motivation with the Responsibility indicator, which provides the greatest support, does not have an indirect influence on the Performance of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development through job satisfaction. This means that the job satisfaction variable is not an intervening variable between the motivation and employee performance variables at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development. The direct influence of motivation through the provision of job responsibilities on the size of the work given by the organization to employees tends to be able to improve employee performance.

7. Leadership on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction

The findings of this study indicate that leadership with personality indicators that provide the most excellent support does not have an indirect influence on the performance of employees of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development through job satisfaction. This means that the job satisfaction variable is not an intervening variable between the motivation and employee performance variables at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development. The direct influence of leaders who foster communication relationships and receive suggestions and input properly from employees tends to improve the performance of employees of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development.

VII. SUGGESTION

Based on the results of research on the Influence of Motivation and Leadership on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development, the following suggestions can be submitted: This research is expected to add insight and knowledge of the author, especially regarding human resource management, especially employee performance, motivation, leadership, and performance satisfaction.

Based on the results of descriptive analysis and research, several suggestions need to be considered for the organization of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development in improving employee performance appraisals in order to meet the targets that have been set for the realization of a world-class government system, including:

Based on the findings of the research, it shows that the Leadership variable with tolerance indicators provides the smallest support, for that it needs to be a consideration for the organization of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development to improve leadership by carrying out leadership training to leaders so that they are better able to understand the personality of a good leader, improve the ability and ability of the leadership, especially to increase the attitude and tolerance of the leadership to subordinates within the Directorate General of Rural Area Development.

The research findings show that the motivation variable with achievement indicators provides the smallest support. It needs to be a consideration for the Directorate General of Rural Area Development organization to increase employee motivation. One of them is by improving employee development management in achieving an employee achievement on an ongoing basis so that employees feel able to achieve an achievement at work.

Based on the research findings, it shows that the Job Satisfaction variable with job indicators and working conditions provides the smallest support, for that it needs to be a consideration for the organization of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development to increase employee job satisfaction. One of them is the placement and provision of employee work in accordance with the main duties and functions held in the employee's position so that the work carried out can assist employees in developing according to the career and field of the employee.

Based on the findings of the research, it shows that the Employee Performance variable with indicators of work quality provides the smallest support, for that it needs to be a consideration for the organization of the Directorate General of Rural Area Development to improve employee performance. one of them is by improving the system in providing training, workshops and learning opportunities to employees in order to be able to improve the quality and abilities of employees on an ongoing basis so that appropriate and satisfactory work results are achieved, as well as improving the implementation of employee quality evaluations which are continuously evaluated in order to improve employee development planning.

It should be considered for the Directorate General of Rural Area Development organization to improve employee performance. One of them is by carrying out activities that can improve employee performance, including providing direction and delivering information to employees, activities to motivate employees, and job satisfaction, which will impact improving employee performance.

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It should be considered for other researchers who will conduct further research, which is expected to add insight and knowledge related to motivation, leadership, job satisfaction, and employee performance. For further research, it is expected to examine several factors of increasing employee performance and motivation, leadership, and job satisfaction, such as work environment variables, competence or compensation, and/or other work units to find out more about improving employee performance.

This research is expected to benefit from the development of science and contribute ideas and expand knowledge about human resource management, especially employee performance, motivation, leadership, and performance satisfaction, to be studied and developed better.

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